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Research article

RNA-seq Analysis of Spinal Cord Tissues After Brachial Plexus Root Avulsion in Mice

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Abstract:

Background Brachial plexus root avulsion (BPRA) can cause motor neuron death, nerve degeneration and upper limb motor dysfunction. The molecular mechanisms of motor neuron death and nerve degeneration are largely unknown and there are no effective therapies to increase the functional recovery after BRPA.

Aim: To detect the early pathway changes in spinal cord tissues after brachial plexus root avulsion.

Methods A mouse brachial plexus avulsion and re-implantation model was constructed, and the C5-C7 segments of the spinal cords were dissected three days after the surgery. We used RNA-seq to identify the expression changes of genes and gene networks in spinal cord tissues.

Results A total of 2253 differentially expressed genes were found significantly changed with 1852 upregulated and 401 downregulated at 3 days after BPRA. Gene ontology (GO) enrichment analysis showed that differentially expressed genes were most enriched in immune system process, regulation of immune system process, defense response, plasma membrane part, extracellular region part, cell surface, protein binding, receptor binding, glycosaminoglycan binding. Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) pathway analysis showed that the most enriched pathways included osteoclast differentiation, NF-kappa B, cytokine-cytokine receptor interaction, TNF, hematopoietic cell lineage, complement and coagulation cascades, PI3K-Akt, ECM-receptor interaction, NOD-like receptor, Toll-like receptor signaling pathway.

Conclusions This study systematically identified the critical genes and signaling pathways in BPRA pathology. These results expand our understanding of the complex molecular mechanisms involved in BPRA and provide a foundation for future research of spinal cord tissue injury and repair.

Key words brachial plexus root avulsion, spinal cord injury, RNA sequencing, signal path analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Brachial plexus is a relatively complex neural network, which is formed by the anterior branch of the lower 4 cervical nerves and the first thoracic nerve (C5-C8 and T1), which could be divided into pre-ganglion part and post-ganglion part by ganglion. Brachial plexus injuries are mainly caused by car accidents, falling and other accidents¹. The pain that often occurs after brachial plexus avulsion imposes an additional burden on the quality of life of patients who have been impaired by motor, sensory, and autonomic dysfunction². This type of lesion represents both CNS damage and PNS damage³. At present, the main clinical treatment is

nerve translocation or nerve root replantation. Previous studies have shown that NRG-1 can promote the recovery of nerve function in brachial plexus nerve injury after contralateral C7 nerve root metastasis in rats⁴. Valproic acid also showed a neuroprotective effect and promoted neurite growth in several peripheral nerve injury models⁵. However, there is still a large gap in the study of brachial plexus injury involving transcriptome level. In this study, RNA-seq technology was used to explore which genes and related signal pathways play a role after brachial plexus avulsion injury, to provide theoretical basis for the improvement and treatment of brachial plexus avulsion injury.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

ANIMAL

Two-month-old C57BL/6J mice were purchased from the Experimental Animal Center of Guangdong Province, China, maintained on a 12-h light/12-h dark cycle, and afford food and water ad libitum at $21 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$.

The Laboratory Animal Ethics Committee at Jinan University approved all experimental protocols. All the efforts were made to minimize pain and discomfort to the experimental animals.

BRACHIAL PLEXUS AVULSION AND RE-IMPLANTATION MODEL

Two-month-old male C57BL/6J mice were anesthetized by intraperitoneal injection of 1.25% avertin and places prone on a surgical table. The C5–C7 segments of the spinal cord were easily identified by their location relative to the long spine of T2. Using unilateral laminectomy of C4 to C7 vertebral plate on the right side, exposed C5- C7 nerve root, the right C5–C7 dorsal and ventral roots were dissected out and avulsed, avoid contact with the spinal cord to establish, then put the C6 segments of the dorsal and ventral nerve root replantation back to its original position. Muscles and skin were sutured in layers, and all animals were returned to their cages after recovery from anesthesia.

TOTAL RNA EXTRACTION

Total RNA was extracted from the tissues using Trizol (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA, USA) according to manual instruction. About 60mg of tissues were ground into powder by liquid nitrogen in a 2mL tube, followed by being homogenized for 2minutes and rested horizontally for 5minutes. The mix was centrifuged for 5minutes at $12,000 \times g$ at 4°C , then the supernatant was transferred into a new EP tube with 0.3mL chloroform/isoamyl alcohol (24:1). The mix was shaken vigorously for 15s, and then centrifuged at $12,000 \times g$ for 10 minutes at 4°C . After centrifugation, the upper aqueous phase where RNA remained was transferred into a new tube with equal volume of supernatant of isopropyl alcohol, then centrifuged at 13,600rpm for 20minutes at 4°C . After deserting the supernatant, the RNA pellet was washed twice with 1mL 75%ethanol, then the mix was centrifuged at 13,600 rpm for 3minutes at 4°C to collect residual ethanol, followed by the pellet air dry for 5-10 minutes in the biosafety cabinet. Finally, 25 μL ~100 μL of DEPC-treated water was added to dissolve the RNA. Subsequently, total RNA was qualified and quantified using a Nano Drop and Agilent 2100 bioanalyzer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, MA, USA).

mRNA LIBRARY CONSTRUCTION

Oligo(dT)-attached magnetic beads were used to purified mRNA. Purified mRNA was fragmented into small pieces with fragment buffer at appropriate temperature. Then First-strand cDNA was generated using random hexamer-primed reverse transcription, followed by a second-strand cDNA synthesis. Afterwards, A-Tailing Mix and RNA Index Adapters were added by incubating to end repair. The cDNA fragments obtained from previous step were amplified by PCR, and products were purified by Ampure XP Beads, then dissolved in EB solution. The product was validated on the Agilent Technologies 2100 bioanalyzer for quality control. The double stranded PCR products from previous step were heated denatured and circularized by the splint oligo sequence to get the final library. The single strand circle DNA (ssCir DNA) was

formatted as the final library. The final library was amplified with phi29 to make DNA nanoball (DNB) which had more than 300 copies of one molecular, DNBS were loaded into the patterned nanoarray and single end 50 bases reads were generated on BGISEQ500 platform (BGI-Shenzhen, China).

DATA ANALYSIS

The sequencing data is called raw reads or raw data. and quality control (QC) is then performed on raw reads to determine whether the sequencing data is suitable for subsequent analysis. After qualified quality control, the filtered clean reads were compared to the reference genome. After alignment, the alignment rate and the distribution of reads on the reference sequence were statistically analyzed to determine whether the alignment result had passed the second QC of alignment. If passed, quantitative analysis of genes, analysis based on gene expression level (principal component, correlation, differential gene screening, etc.), and more in-depth mining and analysis of differential expression genes among selected samples will be conducted.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RNA-Seq was used to examine the differential gene expression profile. A total of 2253 genes were found to have significant changes ($\log_2FC=1$, $P < 0.001$), with 1852 upregulated and 401 downregulated genes (**Fig. 1**).

According to the functional annotation in GO database, the GO enrichment terms of biological processes (BP), cellular component (CC) and molecular function (MF) for DFGs are shown in **Fig. 2**. The seven most-enriched GO biological processes were mainly associated with immune and defense responses. The seven most-enriched GO cellular component were plasma member, extracellular region, cell surface and matrix. The seven most-enriched GO molecular function included protein binding, receptor binding, glycosaminoglycan binding and peptidase regulator activity.

Figure 1 Different gene volcanic map.

The abscissa is the fold change value of the difference in gene or transcript expression between two samples; the ordinate is the statistical test value of the difference in gene or transcript expression, and the P value represents the significance of gene expression, both of which are Logarithmic speech processing of related expression values.

Figure 2 The Gene Ontology (GO) analysis of differentially expresses genes (DEGs).

Bar plot show the top seven enrichment score ($-\log_{10}(Q \text{ value})$) values of the significant enrichment terms of DEGs involving biological process, cellular component, and molecular function.

According to the functional annotation in KEGG database. The DEGs were subjected to KEGG pathway enrichment analysis. The $p \text{ value} < 0.05$ was set as the threshold of significant enrichment (Fig. 3). Based on the KEGG pathway enrichment analysis, The DEGs were significantly enriched in 314 signaling pathways, many of which are involved with the inflammatory response, including NF-kappa B signaling pathway, Cytokine-cytokine receptor interaction, TNF signaling pathway, Hematopoietic cell lineage, PI3K-Akt signaling pathway and complement and coagulation cascades.

Figure 3 Analysis of differential gene KEGG pathway enrichment.

Histogram of KEGG pathway enrichment distribution of DEGs. The bar plot shows the top twenty enrichment score ($-\log_{10}(\text{Q value})$) value of the significant enrichment pathway.

We further observed gene expression changes in related signaling pathways as shown in **Fig. 4**. The Wnt signaling pathway is activated after BPRA, in which the expression of Wnt2, Wnt4 and Wnt6 all have been up-regulated, and Wnt2, Wnt4 and Wnt6 are mediating the Wnt classical signaling pathway. Besides, the expression levels of Wif1, Fzd7 and c-jun were up-regulated and β -catenin was down-regulated (**Fig. 4A**). After spinal cord injury, which leads to axonal demyelination, we detected that the molecules involved in axon guidance also changed after BPRA. Among them, Rac2, CXCR4, Sema3A and PlexinB were up-regulated, and ngl-1, ngl-2, TRPC and CaMKII were down-regulated (**Fig. 4B**). In addition, we also detected upregulation of some inflammatory related factors, such as TNF, IL6, Fas, CD40, NFKB2, c-fos, p38, and CCL2 (**Fig. 4C**).

Figure 4 Differential gene expression analysis of related pathways. A: Changes in genes related to Wnt signaling pathway. B: Changes in genes related to axon guidance. C: Changes in genes related to common activation gene of spinal cord injury.

BRPA results in the complete loss of upper limb motor function, mainly due to the death of spinal cord motor neurons⁶. In order to detect the early pathway changes, through detecting the expression differences at transcriptome level to find the key pathway of potential pathogenicity.

A previous study reported that the PI3K/Akt pathway is involved in the activation of glia after ventral joint dorsal root avulsion⁷, and some studies have shown the expression of PI3K, Akt and p-Akt increased sharply on the first day after SCI injury⁸. Our results also indicate the activation of the PI3K/Akt signaling pathway after BPRA, as well as the up-regulation of c-jun, CREB and other factors. Studies have shown that activation of the PI3K/Akt signaling pathway after spinal cord injury plays a protective role in spinal cord injury, and its activation can alleviate secondary injury caused by primary injury and act as a barrier^{9, 10}. The PI3K/Akt signaling pathway has cross-connection with mTOR signaling pathway, the up-regulation of PI3K activates the phosphorylation of 4EBPs, a key factor in the mTOR signaling pathway, which in turn affects the synthesis of related proteins.

MAPK signaling pathway plays a key role in spinal cord injury and secondary injury after spinal cord injury¹¹. Studies have shown that high expression of signal-regulated kinase and p38MAPK can be detected about 1h after spinal cord injury in rats¹². We also detected activation of the MAPK signaling pathway, the up-regulation of key factors such as c-jun, MKP, p38, and upregulates TNF to activate the TNF signaling pathway. TNF activates TNF- α and phosphorylates P38, causing transcription of factors such as Ccl1, il-6, IL1b and Fos, which leads to cell apoptosis and aggravates the secondary injury.

Wnt signaling pathway plays an important role in neurodevelopment, including neuronal polarization, axon growth, guidance, branching, synaptic formation and structural remodeling¹³. Studies have shown that Wnts are normally not expressed at detectable level in uninjured adult

spinal cord, but after injury, three Wnt genes (Wnt1, Wnt4, and Wnt5a) will rapidly induce expression around the injury site¹⁴. We also detected activation of the Wnt signaling pathway, including activation of Wnt / β -catenin signaling pathway, Wnt/PCP signaling pathway and Wnt/Ca²⁺ signaling pathway. Frizzled is a family of G protein-coupled receptors. As a receptor in the Wnt signaling pathway, its upregulation involves three Wnt signaling pathways. In Wnt / β -catenin signaling pathway. The up regulation of DVL, GBP causes the transcription of target gene and the up regulation of C-Jun, C-Myc, Fra-1 and *cvcD* expression and the regulation of cell cycle. Of note, the expression level of Wnts are up-regulated in Wnt / β -catenin signaling pathway, including Wnt2, Wnt4 and Wnt6. Our research shows that Wnt2, Wnt4, and Wnt6 are mainly activated early after BPRA, but at the same time we also detected the activation of non-classical signals, such as the up-regulation of Rac, PLC, NFAT factor, indicating that non-classical Wnt signaling pathway are also involved in the response after BPRA.

We also detected differences in axon guidance after BPRA. Down-regulation of NGL-1 NGL-2 were detected, Netrin-G1 and Netrin-G2 are trans-synaptic adhesion molecules distributed on different axons. NGL1 and NGL2 are their homologous receptors and are the neurite outgrowth-directing factor G. Ligands, which play a role in regulating axon growth and synapse formation¹⁵. Our test results found that the expression levels of Netrin-G1 and Netrin-G2 did not change, while the expression levels of NGL-1 and NGL-2 were down-regulated, which may be a key factor affecting axon regeneration after BPRA.

The results involved a variety of signaling pathways such as various diseases, GABAergic synapses, glutamatergic synapses, RNA transport, Notch signaling pathway, NOD-like receptors and so on, and many known genes involved in spinal cord injury, such as M-CSF, IL1, TNF α , CD14, P38, CR3, CCL2. In addition, we also found unreported genes, such as BSF, PRR19, Fabp4, Olr1, Ucn3, and some tumor-related genes.

CONCLUSION

Our research not only described the overall changes in gene expression after BPRA in mice, but also systematically identified the key genes and signaling pathways in the pathology. Although the genes related to spinal cord injury and repair are not yet clear, the RNA-seq analysis proposed in this study will help us further understand its complex molecular mechanism and lay the foundation for further research on tissue damage and repair after spinal cord injury.

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